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RADNEXT Transnational Access Summary Report

Project title	<i>DVS and Environment Sensitivity Evaluation for Radiation Vulnerability of COTS SRAMs (*DESERV)</i>
Project TA identifier	TA08-201
General application	
Type of test	SEE, neutron tests
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Co-authors, Institutes	
Date(s) of the experiment	02-2024
Facility	FNG
Amount of access granted (unit of access: 1h)	48

Objectives of the experiments

The effect of SPI communication speed on the SEE sensitivity of three PSRAMs against 14-MeV neutrons is studied. The tested devices, produced by two different manufacturers, come in capacities of 16 Mb and 64 Mb for the AP devices and 32 Mb for the ISSI memory. The devices were tested in both dynamic and static modes to achieve a better comprehension. The memories use both SPI and Quad SPI (QPI).

Experiment test report

Devices Under Test (DUTs) and Experimental Setup

DUTs Overview

Two COTS PSRAMs were tested as Devices Under Test (DUTs):

1. **APS6404L-SQRH** (64Mb) and **APS1604L-3SQR** (16Mb), manufactured by AP Memory Technology.
2. **IS66WVS4M8ALL** (32Mb), manufactured by ISSI Inc.

Unfortunately, the mapping of logical addresses to the physical positions of memory cells was unavailable. However, statistical methods previously outlined by us were employed to classify

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different types of events from the raw data.

Experimental Control System

The DUTs were controlled using a microcontroller board powered by the Atmel SAM3X8E ARM Cortex-M3 CPU, operating at up to 84 MHz. This microcontroller was connected to a computer system via a USB cable, which served two purposes:

- **Power Supply:** *Provided power to the microcontroller and DUTs.*
- **Data Storage:** *Enabled efficient data collection and storage.*

The computer system, housed in a separate room, was used to monitor and control the experiment. To prevent radiation-induced damage, all equipment in the radiation room—except the DUTs—was shielded against radiation.

Testing Campaign

The test campaign was conducted in February 2024 at the **Frascati Neutron Generator (FNG)** in Italy. During the experiment, the DUTs were exposed to **10^9 14-MeV neutrons/cm²**, generated via typical D-T reactions.

Radiation Testing Results

Static Mode Testing

Initially, the memories were tested in static mode to determine a threshold flux for the radiation setup. This testing was conducted using a data pattern of 0x55, with the flux gradually increased.

None of the DUTs (Devices Under Test) exhibited any Single Event Effects (SEEs) up to a flux of **2×10^7 (n/cm²/s)** and a total fluence of **5×10^{10} (n/cm²)**. The absence of Single Bit Upsets (SBUs) aligns with the PSRAM nature of the DUTs.

Dynamic Tests: Raw Results

Due to time constraints, the dynamic tests were conducted at the maximum available flux of **2×10^7 (n/cm²/s)**.

Each DUT was evaluated using two algorithms:

1. **March-C**
2. **DS Algorithm**

The tests were performed at various speeds, and the raw data collected during these

experiments is summarized in this table.

Device	Algorithm	Speed (MHz)	Total Fluence (n/cm^2) $\times 10^{11}$	Number of Observed bitflips
AP (a)	March-C	3	10	×
		4	10	827
		6	10	×
		12	10	33
	DS	4	19.1	6
AP (b)	March-C	3	1.15	×
		4	7.63	×
		4	1.09	235
		6	1.14	×
		12	1.11	6
	DS	12	22.7	16539
		12	20.2	5585
ISSI	March-C	3	1.33	320
		4	1.33	303
		6	1.31	367
		12	1.08	357
	DS	12	18	×

Outcome of the experiments

Please indicate what the experiment is likely to lead to by putting an 'X' next to one or more of the possible outcomes below.

Journal publication	
Data for Thesis	
Follow-up experiment at same facility	X
Follow-up experiment at another facility	
Other	X

As a RADNEXT user, we encourage you to submit the scientific results of your experiments to journals as well as to the NSREC and RADECS data workshops. Please remember to include the RADNEXT acknowledgment into your publications!

RADNEXT acknowledgment:

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